

Theoretical research exploring for universal principles and general description model of life phenomena through the interdisciplinary exploration

An equation regarding golden ratio of ϕ and sigmoid function of σ

$$\phi(1 + e^{-x})^{-1} = (\phi - 1)^{-1}\sigma(x)$$

$$f(x) = \phi(1 + e^{-x})^{-1}$$

$f(x)$ and $f(-x)$ with $x \rightarrow -x$, $-x \rightarrow x$, to arrange recombinantly

This describes double helix structure.

$$f(x)f^{-1}(x) = x^2$$

Therefore, $f(x)$ is thought to be describing for dissipative structure.

Disturbance of absoluteness by fluctuation is separated symmetrically to complementary fluctuation for $f(x)$ and $f^{-1}(x)$.

This describes the symmetry of system separation by dynamic equilibrium, generation of new singularity connecting 0 with ∞ and equivalence of chaotic orbit.

0 and ∞ generate the concepts of positiveness and negativeness and as its perturbation, fluctuations are generated.

This describes the process of forming new coordinate axes as symmetrical axes of coordinate axes, then exploring the edge of chaos where 0 and ∞ connect.

Internal and external renormalization, increase in surface area, increase in heat exchange efficiency

It can be explained as renormalization to relativity.

That is to say, relative axis if symmetry exists as cooperation of 0 and ∞ , which is recursive and self-cooperative explore for the edge of chaos beyond that.

It can be thought that life phenomena are the ones maintained by recursive circulation of cooperation of fluctuation in the absoluteness of entropy and space-time.

More comprehensively, life phenomena are possible to be thought to describe as the ones that dynamic equilibrium of recursive circulation of cooperation of fluctuation in the absoluteness of entropy and space-time are shut up in the paradox by cooperative renormalization of relative fluctuation in the structure degenerating symmetry of broken symmetry, 0 and ∞ are cooperated, through the orientation and request of the internal and external cooperation, it is maintained, deepen and become in more complexity.

Life phenomena, within the dynamism of material interactions, manifest as a recursive dynamism which is more complex, more functional and more stable that interacts with the environment through the cooperative deepening of relative dissipative structures by internal and external renormalization, exploring for more complex symmetry in broken symmetry, by complementarity between diffusivity and convergence communicating about values through entropy and space-time interactions, forming a complex cooperative system of microscopic paradoxes and macroscopic paradoxes through the cooperation of 0 and ∞ , balancing the dynamic equilibrium of adaptive organization of perturbation energy and potential change, capturing meaningful fluctuations, supporting and selecting what is expressed through the adaptive organization of ambivalence, orienting towards and requiring a balance of dynamic equilibrium in recursive, evolutionary, and self-restorative functionality, acquiring new functionality, and exploring for and being explored from the edge of chaos through the deepening internal and external cooperation between 0 and ∞ , thus continuously evolving and adapting.

Life phenomenon is can be described as a paradox that is oriented to and requested from the cooperation of dynamic equilibrium, repeatedly approaching the possible in an attempt to escape the impossible, through the cooperative deepening of fluctuations in space-time and entropy that converge, diffuse, and cooperate the cooperation of 0 and ∞ , through the orientation and request for the complementarity of information on -1 and 1. It is a paradox that is oriented to and required from the cooperation of dynamic equilibrium.

The double helix structure represents a mechanism of life phenomenon that transforms horizontal dynamic equilibrium into vertical dissipative structure, similar to that of a solenoid. Therefore, we considered the regular separation of three-dimensional vectors, like Lorentz force, in the relationship between information and dynamic equilibrium, but could not reach a clear conclusion. However, considering of the mutual transformation between material equivalence and informational inequivalence, we consider the asymmetric interaction of information entropy and nonequilibrium processes. What would happen if they were combined as different systems, creating an inside and an outside? It is a very interesting mechanism.

Recursive and nonlinear perturbations, through the coordination of 0 and ∞ , generate the emergence of cooperation of relative dissipative structures, and in concert with transcendental information about mass and space-time, renormalize and deepen the ambivalence of life phenomena as a cooperation of microscopic paradoxes and macroscopic paradoxes.

It seems that the deepening of these cooperative context is oriented to and requested from the considering the cooperation of 0 and ∞ as an important mechanism in life phenomenon recursively.

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